

Inside AI-PRISM: Progress, Collaboration, and Innovation in 2025

Welcome to AI-PRISM Newsletter #5!

The latest edition of the AI-PRISM Newsletter highlights key milestones achieved in the first 4 months of 2025, reflecting the project's ongoing commitment to advancing human-centred robotics for smart manufacturing.

From new scientific publications and international webinars to high-profile conferences and alliance-building efforts, this issue offers a comprehensive view of AI-PRISM's growing ecosystem and its contributions to Europe's AI and robotics landscape. Discover our latest breakthroughs, revisit project events, and explore opportunities to engage through our Open-Access Alliance.

AI-PRISM Science

AI-Based Positioning on a Micro Scale

PUBLICATIONS

AI-Based Positioning on a Micro Scales

Tomasz Kołcon

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We are continuing our scientific journey with another important publication. The now-published paper "[AI-Based Positioning on a Micro Scale](#)" investigates the use of AI technologies to achieve micrometer-level positioning on semiconductor elements. This paper

was co-authored by Tomasz Kołcon, Iveta Eimontaite, Piotr Gemza, Krystian Gołowski, Miron Kołodziejczyk, and Adam Wołoszczuk.

[Read more](#)

AI-PRISM Journey

AI-PRISM Project Meeting in Athens: Moving Forward with AI-Powered Human-Robot Collaboration

#AIPRISMevents

4th PROJECT MEETING | Athens, Greece | 25th and 26th February 2025

The **4th Plenary Meeting of the AI-PRISM** project, held on 25-26 February 2025 in Athens, provided a general overview of the project's progress, ongoing research, and the future direction as the project moves towards its conclusion.

[Find out more](#)

Tech Advancements

AI-PRISM at ETRI webinar for Korea-EU collaboration

그림 5. 모빌리티UX연구실 윤대섭 실장(맨 왼쪽)을 포함한 국내 연구진 3인(맨 오른쪽)과 AI-PRISM 프로젝트 코디네이터 단체사진, 2024 정규회의(이탈리아)

The Korea-EU Research Centre (KERC) and National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) co-hosted a **webinar on the application process for Korean entities to participate in the Horizon Europe Pillar 2** (global challenges and European industrial competitiveness).

[Read more](#)

Join the Open-Access Alliance!

AI-PRISM
OPEN • ACCESS
ALLIANCE

THE EUROPEAN
DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB
IN TRANSILVANIA

Funded by
the European Union

The **AI-PRISM Open-Access Alliance** builds on the technical solutions and pilot cases from the AI-PRISM project to broaden access to its results. It aims to create a stakeholder ecosystem that supports the reuse of these outcomes in various scenarios, fosters the development of new human-centric, AI-powered smart manufacturing solutions, and drives new business opportunities.

AI-PRISM has just launched a short questionnaire to gather interest from potential stakeholders who would like to join the AI-PRISM Open Access Alliance. If you're interested in becoming a member, we encourage you to complete the form!

Fill in the Questionnaire

2 scientific poster sessions

AI-PRISM Events

Announcing AI-PRISM Workshop on Methods for
Enhancing Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration |
27th May online

CEN WORKSHOP

Methods for enhancing industrial human-
robot collaboration and cooperation

27th MAY | 10.00 | Online

We are pleased to announce, and invite you to the CEN Workshop on "Methods for Enhancing Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration and Cooperation", organized in the framework of the AI-PRISM project. The virtual kick-off meeting will be held on 27 May 2025 at 10.00.

Read more

AI-PRISM's Activities at ERF 2025 – A Week of Engagement, Innovation and Collaboration

aiprism.eu

The **European Robotics Forum 2025 (ERF2025) in Stuttgart** opened with a robust focus on transformation and sustainability in manufacturing. Keynote speaker Dr Joerg Burzer of Mercedes-Benz AG set the tone by presenting how innovative technologies are revolutionizing automotive production for a sustainable future. The opening was also augmented by inputs from leading voices in research, policy, and industry. AI-PRISM made a name for itself with a series of scientific contributions, like the presentation of 2 scientific posters, the participation in 3 Workshops, and public outreach activities across the forum with its own booth in the exhibition area.

[Read more](#)

Dr Daesub Yoon Presents AI-PRISM at K-Water Institute

Dr Daesub Yoon, Section Head of Mobility User Experience Research at ETRI (Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute), delivered a keynote address at the K-Water Institute, Daejeon, South Korea, on 12 March 2025. The session was devoted to sharing Korean experiences in EU-funded research with a particular focus on the AI-PRISM project, a Horizon Europe project committed to human-centered robotics in smart factories.

FreeZeV2.1 – an innovative AI model – Wins Top Award for Object Detection

FreeZeV2.1, an innovative AI model, has just won the "Overall Best Method" at the 2024 BOP Challenge, the leading competition for 6D object pose estimation. Designed by researchers (Andrea Caraffa, Davide Boscaini, Amir Hamza and Fabio Poiesi) at the Technologies of Vision Lab of the Bruno Kessler Foundation, the technology opens pathways towards smarter, more adaptive robots.

[Learn more](#)

[Learn more](#)

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AI-PRISM Horizon Europe

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Horizon Europe – Grant Agreement number 101058589 Funded by the European Union.

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